
Review of Functional Approach to Professional Discourse Exploration in Linguistics

Lei Li

Guangdong Polytechnic College, Zhaoqing, Guangdong Province 225127, China

Abstract: *Functional Approach to Professional Discourse Exploration in Linguistics provides an account of the study on various professional discourse in the realm of a functional linguistic method, underlining the approach to communicative efficacy in professional discourse. Additionally, the book addresses a wide range of themes, including the structural, semantic, cognitive, and pragmatic features of professional speech, argumentative strategies, humor in a professional speech, and word-building processes, primarily from the practical point of the speech. As such, the volume is refreshingly comprehensive and cutting-edge accompanied by 10 contributions to discuss each discourse in an accessible way.*

Keywords: Professional speech; discourse; functional linguistics

I. Introduction

In *Functional Approach to Professional Discourse Exploration in Linguistics*, The introductory section presents a general basis for professional communication effectiveness in light of functional linguistics centering on the discursive nature of language use (van Dijk 1992). Also, it offers the reader both a picture of the historical evolution of functionalism and a basic structure for its application in various discourses. It is the complexity of social communication that makes it logically necessary to update or elucidate current linguistic practices with the latest professional discourse methods.

II. Term system in British and Russian language

Olga et al. conduct a holistic and scientific exploration of the term system in British and Russian languages. They take into account the extensive character of term nomination within the course of scholarly lexical renewal and uncover the tendencies of lexical systems in terms of their construction and semantics. The dramatic development of technology determines the necessity for linguistics research into codes of communication, practical regulations, and rituals.

Olga et al., intend to disclose various syntactic techniques that generate or foster the expressive force of advertising texts and to investigate their expressive capabilities in the construction of such texts. It attests the potential of the advertising discourse to facilitate the expressive syntactic devices to develop into stylistic and practical ones.

Elena et al., state despite the increasing fashion for humor to address economic concerns, economic discourse is nonetheless rigorously institutional, implying that the proper appreciation of economic humor still demands adequate background knowledge that underpins the community status of economists as part of a certain language community. Victoria V. Sibul et al., specifically examine the utility of precedent texts' citations of such discourses in realizing the pragmatic ends attributed to them. They, based on quantitative analysis of pertinent literature, review precedents titles and documents, analyze their operational potential and ascertain the spectrum of precedent texts' origins.

III. Political discourse analysis

Samvel and Maria assert that argumentative structure in political discourse comprises descriptive and evaluative components and it resides on those aspects of persuasion: rational regimes and irrational approach, through which the persuasive power of an argument is reinforced since they are associated with the speaker's practical aims and the communicative situation. Lyudmila and Juliya propose discursive construction of the "other" in British political communication from the perspective of linguistic semiotics and linguistic pragmatics. They advance a paradigm 'with four fundamental tactics and 21 discourse-symbolic devices' (p199) that display "otherness", which has certain implications in the current cross-cultural exchange.

Elizaveta et al. describe the mutually reinforcing relationship between psychological constructions within the human brain, its linguistic representations, and the complicated active structure of discourse, i.e., the medical discourse drawing on cognitive and functional linguistics. Such a method empowers researchers to specify the connotations of professional linguistic concepts and to sketch out novel research angles for medical discourse analysis.

Igor et al. reveal that discourse is created by the interaction of diverse elements. Although the construction is not definitive, it does carry a model of synergistic development in which institutional discourse permeates personal discourse. The authors identify six essential professional discourse situations, i.e., 'conflict, deal, crisis, instruction, interview, relaxation' (P299). These situations are certainly noteworthy and have triggered functional analysis regarding the fragments of professional discourse.

IV. Implications of professional discourse

Galina et al. approach conversion as a means to rich the word with the case study of professional terms in the domain of "Fashion", observing conversion as a hallmark of such an integral trait of language creativity in the contemporary social setting. The purpose of the essay is to ascertain the conversion position in the French fashion paralinguistic lexical construction body and to reveal the extent of its fertilization in contemporary French.

In all, the volume is conducive to the identification of prospective tendencies throughout the linguistic community. It presents state-of-the-art studies regarding distinct genres of specialized discourse. Professional language practices are examined in terms of functional linguistics and the effects of speech on the receiver and the problem of feedback in interaction are also illuminated.

Nevertheless, the book contains shortcomings to varying degrees. On the one hand, readers will get a deeper knowledge of the theme of distinct professional discourse if there could have been a conclusion part in the end. On the other hand, what is obvious is that most research materials are concerned with authors' experience which is expected to extend to more ample contexts to attract more attention.

V. Conclusion

Regardless, this book enlightens readers to contemplate the role of functionalism in other discourse and extralinguistic impact on a wide range of professional discourse. Scholars and practitioners will more or less recognize the book as extensive, instructive, and informative in that it not only elaborates the status quo of functionalism in academic discourse, political discourse, media discourse, economic discourse, medical discourse, and fashion area but also provide prospective trends in those and other professional discourse, particularly in the present COVID-19 situation. All elements considered, the volume provides much-needed material for scholars who are interested in discourse studies and is indeed a timely supplement to the unsystematic journal thesis currently in circulation in this regard.

Reference

- [1.] van Dijk, T. A. (1992). *Text and context. Explorations in the semantics and pragmatics of discourse.* Longman.